

Short Communication

Colloidal stability of 2D MoS₂ obtained via liquid-phase exfoliation using Water and Tween 20Jaroslava Jarolímková^{a,*}, Viktorie Neubertová^a, Adéla Jagerová^b, Zdeňka Kolská^a^a Centre for Nanomaterials and Biotechnology, Faculty of Science, J. E. Purkyně University, Pasteurova 15, 40096 Ústí nad Labem, Czech Republic^b Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, J. E. Purkyně University, Pasteurova 15, 40096 Ústí nad Labem, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

We report a facile and potentially scalable aqueous liquid-phase exfoliation of MoS₂ using the nonionic surfactant Tween 20 and a conventional high-shear mixer. The influence of shear time on flake size, electrokinetic potential, and colloidal stability was systematically investigated. Increasing exfoliation time led to a reduction in apparent particle size and a shift of the electrokinetic potential toward more negative values, indicating improved dispersion stability. The most exfoliated sample exhibited a sedimentation exponent ($\alpha \approx 0.20$), corresponding to slow sedimentation and enhanced colloidal stability. The concentration of dispersed material increased with shear time, reaching 0.017 mg mL⁻¹, with approximately 51% retention after 28 days. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first to address liquid exfoliation of MoS₂ in water with the addition of the Tween 20. The approach is environmentally benign, inexpensive and yields stable aqueous MoS₂ dispersions suitable for further processing and application.

1. Introduction

Two dimensional (2D) materials have attracted attention due to their unique structural, electronic, optical, and mechanical properties that are different from their bulk counterparts [1–3]. Among them, transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) represent an important class of layered semiconductors with tunable band gaps and strong light–matter interactions. These properties make 2D TMDs very attractive for a wide range of applications, including optoelectronics [4,5], photodetectors [1,6], energy storage, conversion and catalysts [7–10].

Various approaches have been developed to produce 2D TMDs, ranging from low-yield micromechanical exfoliation (“Scotch tape method”) [11,12] to higher-yield methods such as chemical lithium intercalation [7,13] and liquid-phase exfoliation (LPE) [2,4,6,8,14]. In LPE, bulk TMDs powder is dispersed in a suitable medium and subjected to mechanical treatment, typically via ultrasonication [2,4,6,8,14] or high-shear mixing [2]. The undisputed advantage of LPE is its scalability, versatility and ability to preserve the internal crystal structure of exfoliated nanosheets. At the same time, control over the thickness of the nanosheets, lateral dimensions and surface chemistry is possible [15]. Recent studies have shown that rational design of the liquid environment can significantly improve the exfoliation efficiency by

increasing the intermolecular and interfacial interactions between solvent molecules and TMDs layers, thereby reducing interlayer van der Waals forces and stabilizing the exfoliated nanosheets against reaggregation [6,16,17]. The selection of the liquid medium is a critical parameter, as it strongly influences exfoliation efficiency and nanosheet stability. While organic solvents [2,18] have traditionally been employed, they are increasingly being substituted by less toxic alcohols [6,8,14] in response to environmental considerations.

Stabilization of 2D MoS₂ in aqueous dispersions is commonly achieved by surfactants. Ionic surfactants adsorb on the MoS₂ surface and prevent aggregation through electrostatic repulsion or micelle formation [19–21]. In contrast, nonionic surfactants generally exhibit lower critical micelle concentrations (CMC), biodegradability, reduced toxicity and can stabilize hydrophobic nanoparticles without disrupting the electronic structure of the material [22,23]. The effect of surfactant concentration on LPE and dispersion stability is strongly nonlinear and depends on the balance between surface adsorption and micellization. At concentrations below or close to the CMC, exfoliation efficiency is often limited by insufficient surface coverage of freshly generated nanosheets, which promotes rapid reaggregation. Increasing the surfactant concentration above the CMC allows the formation of a dense adsorption layer and micellar reservoirs that continuously deliver

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Table 1Results of DLS and ELS analyses for all 2D MoS₂ samples.

Sample	Hydrodynamic diameter [nm]	Peak 1 intensity [nm]	Peak 2 intensity [nm]	Electrokinetic potential [mV]
MoS ₂ -0.5	372 ± 46	302 ± 11	3825 ± 417	-27.7 ± 0.8
MoS ₂ -1	305 ± 12	268 ± 7	3899 ± 416	-29.6 ± 0.9
MoS ₂ -2	281 ± 17	252 ± 7	2519 ± 187	-32.0 ± 0.7

surfactant molecules to newly exposed interfaces, thereby increasing exfoliation yield and long-term colloidal stability [24,25].

Tween 20 (polysorbate 20) is a nonionic surfactant with a high hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB ≈ 16.7) that provides excellent water solubility and strong steric stabilization of dispersed nanomaterials [26]. Tween 20 reduces interfacial tension and stabilizes dispersions through steric, rather than electrostatic, mechanisms. This makes it less sensitive to ionic strength or pH changes than charged or zwitterionic surfactants and enables robust colloidal stabilization in aqueous systems [27]. Compared to other nonionic analogues such as Tween 80, the shorter chain and higher hydrophilicity of Tween 20 promote faster interfacial adsorption and higher emulsification capacity, which improves dispersion stability in polar media [28]. Tween 20 is an attractive nonionic surfactant due to its ability to provide steric stabilization [29] and maintain good dispersibility of MoS₂ flakes in water. Despite these advantages, to the best of our knowledge, no publications have addressed the use of Tween 20 for LPE of TMDs in water. Therefore, this study focuses on the aqueous exfoliation of MoS₂ in the presence of Tween 20 and evaluates the stability of the resulting dispersions using UV-Vis spectroscopy. This combination could provide a significantly more environmentally friendly alternative to conventional organic solvents or ionic surfactant systems.

2. Methods

2.1. Sample preparation

Bulk MoS₂ powder (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) was exfoliated by LPE using a high-shear mixer. A total of 200 mg of MoS₂ were mixed with 100 ml of stock solution. The stock solution was made by mixing 1000 ml of distilled water and 460 μl of Tween 20 (Sigma-Aldrich, France). Taking into account the density of Tween 20 (1.1 g·mL⁻¹) and its average molecular weight (1227 g·mol⁻¹), this corresponds to a molar concentration of approximately 0.41 mM. The Tween 20 concentration corresponds to

approximately 5 × its CMC [26], which ensures well-established formation and effective steric stabilization required for dispersing 2D MoS₂ flakes in water. The exfoliation was performed using a high-shear mixer (Witeg HG-15D, Germany) at 10,000 RPM for 0.5, 1 and 2 h. Next, centrifugation was performed to separate the non-exfoliated MoS₂ with the rotation speed set to 1500 RPM for 5 min. A uniform centrifugation speed of 1500 RPM was used for all samples to enable direct comparison of sedimentation behavior. For more highly exfoliated samples (e.g., MoS₂-2), a higher centrifugation speed would likely remove residual aggregates more effectively and could lead to earlier colloidal stabilization, but a constant speed was deliberately maintained to ensure dataset consistency. The obtained supernatant containing exfoliated MoS₂ nanosheets (2D MoS₂) was labelled as MoS₂-0.5, MoS₂-1, MoS₂-2. A control exfoliation was attempted in pure water, but after centrifugation at 1500 RPM, no yield was observed in the supernatant. Therefore, only the exfoliation with Tween 20 was analyzed.

2.2. Characterization techniques

The hydrodynamic diameter and electrokinetic potential of the 2D MoS₂ was determined using a LitesizerTM 500 (Anton Paar, Graz, Austria). The samples were dispersed in distilled water with pH ~ 5.5 for transmittance ~ 80 % at 25 °C under a detection angle of 175° immediately after synthesis with an error below 5 %. Electrokinetic potential was calculated using the Smoluchowski approximation method.

For the atomic force microscopy (AFM), the samples were prepared by dipping onto a silicon wafer and left in a fume hood until the solution evaporated completely. The AFM measurements were performed using AFM NTEGRA Aura (NT-MDT, Russia) in semi-contact mode using silicon probes (resonant frequency of 183 kHz, force constant of 6 N/m). The collected scans were analyzed using Gwyddion software (version 2.64) [30].

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed using an SU5000 instrument (Hitachi High-Tech Corporation, Tokyo, Japan). Samples for analysis were prepared by drop-casting the colloid onto a silicon wafer, followed by solvent evaporation. The samples were coated with a 20 nm layer of gold. Measurements were carried out at an accelerating voltage of 20 kV. The resulting images were processed using the ImageJ software, and the average lateral size of the MoS₂ flakes was determined.

Samples for UV-Vis analysis were divided into 10 vials containing the same amount of sample. Analysis for colloid stability was performed at 0, 1, 4, 8, 24 and 48 h and subsequently after 7, 14, 21 and 28 days. Measurements were performed in 1.4 ml microcuvettes using a Cary 300 UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA,

Fig. 1. Comparison of AFM images for MoS₂-2 sample in (A) height and (B) phase mode.

Fig. 2. AFM images and height profiles of MoS₂ flakes exfoliated with Tween 20 for (A, B) MoS₂-0.5, (C, D) MoS₂-1 and (E, F) MoS₂-2 samples.

Fig. 3. Histograms of heights for MoS₂ samples prepared using different mixing times.

USA) in the wavelength range of 200–800 nm. The concentration of exfoliated MoS₂ was quantified based on the Beer-Lambert law (1):

$$A = \varepsilon \cdot l \cdot C \quad (1)$$

where: A is absorbance, ε is extinction coefficient, l is cuvette length, and C is concentration. We utilized the extinction coefficient determined for shear-exfoliated MoS₂ by Varrla et al. [31], specifically $\varepsilon_{345\text{nm}} = 68.2 \text{ mL mg}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, a wavelength chosen for its independence of nanosheet size. For the graphical representation of results, absorbance spectra were analyzed as measured raw values for both concentration quantification and peak shift evaluation. Sedimentation kinetics were assessed based on the normalized absorbance (A/A_0) monitored at 800 nm and analyzed using a double-logarithmic plot.

3. Results

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) and electrophoretic light scattering (ELS) analyses were performed on all samples, as shown in Table 1. These results show that the longer the colloid is exposed to the high-shear mixer, the smaller the particles in the colloid are formed. Electrokinetic potential became more negative with decreasing flake size, which typically correlates with improved colloidal stability. This negative surface charge is primarily attributed to the intrinsic surface chemistry of MoS₂ nanosheets, including edge defects, sulfur vacancies, and partially oxidized sites that can generate negatively charged surface

groups or promote preferential adsorption of hydroxyl ions in aqueous environments [9]. The most extreme result was achieved for the MoS₂-2 sample, which has an electrokinetic potential value of $>|30| \text{ mV}$, which indicates the potentially highest stability of the colloidal solution [21]. The adsorption of Tween 20 is expected mainly to provide steric stabilization, while its interfacial arrangement may shift the shear plane and thereby slightly influence the measured electrokinetic potential without introducing significant electrostatic charge. The original bulk powder was analyzed in our previous work with hydrodynamic diameter $\sim 2500 \pm 400 \text{ nm}$ [8]. The second peak in our results is attributed to the limitations of intensity-weighted DLS, which is known to overestimate hydrodynamic diameters for plate like 2D particles due to scattering biases toward larger aggregates. Therefore, DLS is used here primarily to monitor relative trends rather than to determine absolute flake size. DLS provides an apparent hydrodynamic size reflecting aggregates rather than true lateral flake dimensions.

The AFM images (Figs. 1 and 2) show the morphology of the dried MoS₂ dispersions stabilized with Tween 20. A surfactant layer surrounding the MoS₂ flakes is clearly observed in all samples. This indicates strong adsorption of Tween 20 onto the surface of the nanosheets. As a result, the measured AFM heights reflect the combined contribution of the MoS₂ flakes and the associated surfactant coating, rather than the intrinsic thickness of the MoS₂ itself. Therefore, AFM analysis is not used here to determine the number of layers, but instead to qualitatively assess the changes in morphology, aggregation behavior, and relative dimensions of the flakes as a function of mixing time.

Fig. 4. SEM images of (A) bulk powder MoS₂, (B) MoS₂-0.5, (C) MoS₂-1 and (D) MoS₂-2 flakes for lateral size determination.

To better assess the differences between the individual mixing times, the flake height distributions (from 40 flakes) are presented in Fig. 3. For the MoS₂-0.5 sample, corresponding to the shortest mixing time, large aggregated objects with mean height of 163 ± 27 nm are observed (Fig. 2A, 2B). This indicates incomplete disintegration of the bulk material and extensive aggregation during drying. After increasing the mixing time to obtain the MoS₂-1 sample, the apparent height decrease, in mean height to 70 ± 33 nm (Fig. 2C, 2D), which is accompanied by a more homogeneous surface coverage and reduced aggregation. The longest mixed sample, MoS₂-2, exhibits the smallest object characterized with mean height of 30 ± 14 nm (Fig. 2E, 2F).

These systematic changes in apparent height and surface morphology with increasing mixing time indicate the gradual disintegration of larger aggregates and improved dispersion stability. The AFM observation are qualitatively consistent with the trends obtained from DLS and ELS measurements (Table 1). Overall, the AFM results support the conclusion that prolonged mixing promotes the formation of more uniformly dispersed, surfactant-stabilized MoS₂ nanosheets.

The lateral size of MoS₂ flakes was evaluated from SEM images (Fig. 4) using ImageJ software. The bulk precursor (4A) exhibits large, aggregated particles, whereas all exfoliated samples (4B–4D) show a clear reduction in flake size. The average lateral sizes were determined to be 1029 ± 240 nm for MoS₂-0.5, 962 ± 323 nm for MoS₂-1, and 688 ± 135 nm for MoS₂-2.

A gradual decrease in lateral size with increasing exfoliation time indicates that prolonged high-shear mixing promotes not only

exfoliation but also progressive fragmentation of MoS₂ flakes. This trend is consistent with previous reports on liquid-phase exfoliation, where shear forces lead to a trade-off between flake thickness reduction and lateral size decrease [32].

UV-Vis spectroscopy provides detailed insight into changes in MoS₂ dispersion during sedimentation and allows comparison of samples with different degrees of exfoliation (Fig. 5). Fig. 5A presents spectra measured immediately after preparation (0 h) and after 28 days of sedimentation. In the 350–500 nm region, a broad band with overlapping maxima corresponding to excitons C and D is visible. The distinctiveness of this band is a sensitive indicator of exfoliation [33]. In the most exfoliated MoS₂-2 the double-peak structure is pronounced, typical for the semiconducting 2H-phase structure of MoS₂ [10]. In MoS₂-1 it is less distinct, and in MoS₂-0.5 it nearly merges. This confirms that exciton transitions C and D are optically more pronounced in thinner nanosheets, while thicker flakes blur the band [3]. The clear visibility of these high-energy excitons (C and D in the range of 400–450 nm) together with the characteristic peaks A and B confirms the chemical integrity of the nanolayers. Significant oxidation would lead to degradation of the crystal lattice, causing these specific exciton properties to disappear or become indistinguishable from the background.

Fig. 5B shows the time evolution of the position of exciton A. All samples exhibit a gradual blue-shift, corresponding to an increase in exciton energy from values typical of multilayer flakes towards those of few-layer nanosheets. This reflects selective particle sedimentation, where larger flakes gradually settle and thinner layers remain dispersed.

Fig. 5. UV-Vis characterization and sedimentation kinetics of all samples. (A) Representative UV-Vis spectra of samples measured immediately after preparation and after 28 days of sedimentation, (B) Time evolution of the exciton A peak position for all samples, (C) Normalized absorbance at 800 nm (A/A_0) as a function of time, (D) Log-log plot of normalized absorbance ($\ln(A/A_0)$) versus $\ln(t)$ with linear fits used to extract the sedimentation exponent α .

Table 2

Results of the quantitative analysis of MoS₂ dispersions of freshly prepared flakes and after 28 days of aging. Concentrations were determined via UV-Vis absorbance at 345 nm ($\epsilon_{345\text{nm}} = 68.2 \text{ mL mg}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

Sample	Absorbance (fresh flakes)	Conc. (0 hour) [$\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$]	Yield [%]	Absorbance (day 28)	Conc. (day 28) [$\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$]	Retention [%]
MoS ₂ -0.5	0.624	0.009	0.46	0.124	0.002	~20 %
MoS ₂ -1	0.823	0.012	0.6	0.372	0.005	~45 %
MoS ₂ -2	1.147	0.017	0.84	0.582	0.009	~51 %

According to the literature, bulk MoS₂ (10+ layers) typically exhibits exciton A at approximately 1.78–1.80 eV (689–696 nm), multilayer MoS₂ with 3–5 layers lies around ~1.82–1.84 eV (674–681 nm), bilayer MoS₂ appears near 1.85–1.87 eV (664–670 nm) and monolayer MoS₂ is reported at 1.88–1.90 eV (653–660 nm) [34,35].

Fig. 5C illustrates normalized absorbance at 800 nm, chosen outside excitonic transitions to monitor overall particle concentration. All samples show decreasing absorbance with time, reflecting progressive sedimentation. The rate of decrease differs between samples. MoS₂-0.5 sediments fastest (0.35 after 24 h, ~0.08 after 7 days), MoS₂-1 shows intermediate behavior (~0.42 after 24 h, ~0.23 after 7 days), while MoS₂-2 declines slowest (~0.57 after 24 h, ~0.34 after 7 days), indicating the highest colloidal stability.

Fig. 5D demonstrates the log-log plot of normalized absorbance at 800 nm, expressed as $\ln(A/A_0)$, versus $\ln(t)$, which linearizes sedimentation kinetics according to the power-law relation $A_t/A_0 \propto t^{-\alpha}$. The

slope of the fitted line corresponds to $-\alpha$, where α is the sedimentation exponent. The regression analysis yielded values of $\alpha = 0.50$ for MoS₂-0.5, $\alpha = 0.27$ for MoS₂-1 and $\alpha = 0.20$ for MoS₂-2, with coefficients of determination R^2 between 0.96 and 0.97. In comparison with previous studies, Forsberg et al. reported rapid sedimentation in pure water (half-life ~23 h), consistent with higher α values [36]. Sim et al. demonstrated long-term stability after solvent thermal treatment in NMP (~0.2–0.3) [37]. Alharbi and Raston achieved stable dispersions for 3 months using high-shear exfoliation in a vortex fluidic device [38]. Our results follow these trends. MoS₂-0.5 sediments quickly, MoS₂-1 shows intermediate stability and MoS₂-2 ($\alpha = 0.20$) is consistent with values observed for highly stable dispersions [37]. Importantly, this stability was achieved using only a conventional homogenizer as a high-shear mixer together with Tween 20 as a simple surfactant. The method is straightforward, inexpensive and offers a practical advantage for potentially scalable preparation of 2D colloids.

Table 2 summarizes the quantitative analysis. The exfoliation yield increased with shear time and reached 0.84 % (0.017 mg mL⁻¹) for the 2 h sample. This sample also exhibited the highest stability. It retained ~51 % of the dispersed material after 28 days.

For comparison, a study by Smith et al. on LPE of MoS₂ with the assistance of aqueous surfactants reported dispersed concentrations in the order of 0.06–0.09 mg mL⁻¹. The lowest value was for LPE using sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS), while the highest concentration was achieved using TritonX-100. A total of 8 surfactants were studied. Concentrations were determined after centrifugation by UV–Vis spectroscopy using known absorption coefficients [39]. Direct quantitative comparisons are complicated by differences in sonication conditions and centrifugation protocols, but these values provide a useful reference point for assessing dispersion efficiency. The concentrations obtained in our work (Table 2) fall into the same order, suggesting a performance comparable to established aqueous surfactant-based exfoliation approaches.

4. Conclusion

Aqueous liquid-phase exfoliation of MoS₂ in the presence of Tween 20 was shown to produce stable dispersion with properties dependent on applied shear time. Prolonged mixing resulted in smaller lateral flake sizes, more negative electrokinetic potential, and slower sedimentation, indicating improved colloidal stability. The observed stabilization is primarily attributed to steric effects associated with surfactant adsorption, supported by sedimentation kinetics and zeta potential values. Microscopy techniques confirmed gradual fragmentation and improved dispersion homogeneity, while UV–Vis analysis indicated preservation of the MoS₂ structure and selective sedimentation of thicker flakes over time. Although the achieved concentrations are comparable to previously reported aqueous surfactant systems, the method relies on a simple experimental setup without the need for organic solvents or complex processing. Overall, the approach provides a reproducible and potentially scalable route for preparing aqueous MoS₂ dispersions.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at [10.5281/zenodo.17799255](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17799255).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jaroslava Jarolímková: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Viktorie Neubertová:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Adéla Jagerová:** Investigation. **Zdenka Kolská:** Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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